

Education On Environmental Protection By Using Green Energy In Vietnam

Nguyen Thi Hai Yen

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Environmental protection, Green energy, Vietnam</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5138014</p>	<p><i>Green energy consist of the energy that produced by wind, solar, biogas, geothermal, low-impact hydroelectric, and some qualified biomass sources. However, overheating the development of solar projects has been leading to the risk of the national grid and electricity system. In addition, the electricity industry depends on large dam hydropower, coal-fired, and gas-fired in Vietnam recently is also not the best solution for sustainable energy development. Rooftop solar electricity is a good solution for that issue. This research concentrate on rooftop solar and encourage people to invest in that kind of energy to solve the issue and help protect the environment. The survey was conducted in the Central Highland of Vietnam. The results indicate that age and gender had a negative effect on encouragement for such a system investment. Other factors included education, family members, rooftop material, income per family member and level of electricity consumption had a positive effect, in which education has the most effect on encouragement.</i></p>

Introduction

In Vietnam, 90% of the electricity has been producing from gas, coal, and large dam hydropower resources (EVN, 2016, 2017, 2018). However, electricity production will be unstable because of the water's level release and electricity deficiencies that can occur routinely amid the hot weather, and shortage power during the busy period has created security challenges for Vietnam's power segment (Hoang et al., 2011). Especially, according to Power Development Master Plan (PDP) VII revised, no new coal-power plant in the future (Decision 428/QD-TTg, 2016), the dependence on imported fuel will rise rapidly to 51 per cent-60 percent by 2030, then 63 -75% by 2050 across the scenarios (EREA & DEA, 2019).

The Vietnamese Government has been enacted some policies that encourage the development of renewable energy resources (Decision 37/2011/QD-TTg, 2011; Decision No. 11 /2017/QD-TTg, 2017; Decision No. 24/2014/QD-TTg, 2014). There are many solar power projects have been built in Quangtri, Hue, Vungtau, NinhThuan, BinhThuan, Daklak, Tayninh, Binhphuoc, Gialai, Lamdong, Angiang (DEVI, 2020). However, the overheating development of solar power projects focusing on areas with large radiation sources has led to the risk of grid overload and unsafe operation of electricity systems. Some studies showed that the stability of the national electricity grid system depends on large-scale PV generation (Shah et al., 2012, 2015; Tamimi et al., 2013; Tan & Kirschen, 2007; Zhang et al., 2012). Palmer has demonstrated that the UK national electricity grid is exposed to the little risks of the electricity generated by large scale PV (Palmer et al., 2017). In Vietnam, by the end of January 2020, the total capacity of solar energy connected to the grid was 5,404MW (DEVI, 2020). This is far beyond the expected amount of the revised PDP VII (only 850 MW solar power in 2020). In particular, the two provinces of NinhThuan and BinhThuan currently have 38 wind and solar power plants, with a total installed capacity of 2,027 MW. It is expected that by December 2020, wind and solar power capacity in these two provinces will increase to 4,240 MW. While the local capacity is very large, the demand for an additional charge of NinhThuan and BinhThuan is very small, leading to the fact that most of the transmission grid lines, from 110-500 kV in the area are overloaded, including overload lines up to 360%. The shortage power supply still occurs in some areas while PV projects have to cut down 30 – 35% of the capacity that is wasted and damages for the investors and the Electricity corporation of Vietnam (EVN) (Vietnamenergy, 2020). Eleonora et al. (2020), also mentioned the weakness of the grid infrastructure that led to difficulties in developing large-scale of solar PV in Vietnam (Sanseverino et al., 2020). The operational challenges and problems of 500kV line electricity system of Vietnam was illustrated in the study of Hai&Huu (Hai & Huu, 2011).

Rooftop solar electricity system (rooftop PV) is solar PV that installed on a small scale on residential houses, commercial building roofs, factory roofs, plants with a scale of several kW to MW. It also serves the electricity self-consumption of households, businesses, factories, and non-business units, reduces dependence on the national grid, and reduces pressure on the grid (Camilo et al., 2017; Luthander et al., 2015; Roberts et al., 2019;

Rodrigues et al., 2016; Roulot & Raineri, 2018; Tongsopit et al., 2019; Vieira et al., 2017; Widén, 2014). Rooftop solar may resolve the problem of the risk of grid overload and maintain the safety of the grid electricity system.

Method

Data collection

Socioeconomic attributes of the responses such as age, gender, education, marital status, and level of electricity consumption were obtained.

The main research was conducted after a pre-survey with a draft questionnaire to make sure that all the respondents in the main survey can understand all the items of the questionnaire. The survey was performed with 300 household in the study area from May to July 2019 selected purposively by convenience sampling. Only participations, which had not install rooftop solar electricity and had an appropriated rooftop for investment the system was conducted.

Data analysis

A binaryprobit model was used for analyzing households' encouragement for SG rooftop solar electricity system as equation 4 below.

$$Y = \beta'X + \varepsilon$$

Y: Dependent variable: encouragement for SG rooftop solar electricity system investment

β' : Valuation of the coefficient

X: Independent variables: age, gender, number of family members, education, rooftop material, households' income, and electricity consumption.

The probabilities of Y and other statistical analyses was carried out by SPSS v.22 software

Results and Discussion

Respondents' profile

The research was handling in Daklak province with a sample of 300 households, in which, 100% married, 49% was female. Most households have consumed power as levels 3 and 4 respectively 39.7% and 29%. The detail of households' information is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Households' information

	Section	Number	%
	Total (households)	300	100
Age (years old)	20 to 30	7	2.3
	31 to 40	109	36.3
	41 to 50	125	41.7
	51 to 60	55	18.3
	>60	4	1.3
Gender	Man	153	51.0
	Woman	147	49.0
Education	junior school	0	0
	junior high school	2	0.7
	High school	160	53.3
	Undergraduate	102	34.0
	Postgraduate	36	12.0
Marital status	Married	300	100
SG rooftop solar system status	Don't have PV system	300	100
Rooftop material	Corrugated iron	144	4
	Tile	67	22.3
	Concrete flat	36	12

	Section	Number	%
	Total (households)	300	100
	Other	53	17.7
Electricity consumption (kWh)	0 to 50	0	0
	51 to 100	49	16.3
	101 to 200	119	39.7
	201 to 300	87	29.0
	301 to 400	31	10.3
	Over 400	14	4.7

Source: Households survey in the study area.

Binary probit model

The binary probit model was applied to estimate encouragement for SG rooftop PV of the sample 300 households in Daklak province. As mentioned above, encouragement was a binary dependent variable, in which, 1 means that people willing to pay for SG rooftop PV and 0 are vice versa. The independent variables comprise age, gender, number of family members in a household (Family members), education of the despondence (Education), power consumption level (Level_electricity_consum), material of rooftop, and income per family member of each household (Incom_per_family_member).

The model used to estimate encouragement was as following.

$$\text{Encouragement}^* = \beta'_0 + \beta'_1 \text{Age} + \beta'_2 \text{Gender} + \beta'_3 \text{Family_members} + \beta'_4 \text{Education} + \beta'_5 \text{Rooftop_material} + \beta'_6 \text{Level_electricity_consum} + \beta'_7 \text{Incom_per_family_member} + \varepsilon'$$

The model information illustrated in table 2

Table 2. Information about the model

Dependent Variable	Encouragement ^a
Probability Distribution	Binomial
Link Function	Probit

a. The procedure models Willing to pay as the response, treating Do not willing to pay as the reference category.

The correlation between independent variables and encouragement was shown in table 3. In which, all the Sig. values were less than 0.05, thus, encouragement was significantly affected by the independent variables, namely, Age, Gender, Education, Family_members, Rooftop_material, Incom_per_family_member, and Level_electricity_consum. The coefficient β' of Age and Gender are negative, it indicated that younger people and men would have more encouragement for SG rooftop PV than older people and women. The effects of the other variables are all positive. Variable Education had the highest β' , which illustrated the highest effect on encouragement for sg rooftop pv. the level of electricity consumption had a significant effect on encouragement.

Table 3. the effect of independent variables to encouragement

Parameter	β'	Std. Error	Z	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
PROBIT ^a Age	-.067	.079	-.839	.401	-.222	.089
Gender	-.096	.120	-.804	.422	-.331	.138
Education	.322	.081	3.969	.000	.163	.481
Family_members	.170	.075	2.252	.024	.022	.318
Rooftop_material	.050	.050	1.004	.315	-.048	.148
Incom_per_family_member	.000	.000	4.731	.000	.000	.000
Level_electricity_consum	.234	.057	4.121	.000	.123	.346
Intercept	-4.151	.483	-8.598	.000	-4.634	-3.668

a. PROBIT model: PROBIT(p) = Intercept + β' X

Discussion

There are off-grid, hybrid, and smart-grid rooftop PV, the study concentrated only on the encouragement for SG system. In addition, only the Central Highlands, which has the highest sunshine duration each year, was

conducted, although all parts of Vietnam are suitable for solar electricity development. Only the households who have got married were analyzed.

This study offers crucial information statistics for the policy makers to encourage people for using green energy instead of conventional energy. The study shows that education and level of power consumption were important factors that effect on encouragement. Therefore, the government should communicate and provide incentives directly to the households who had high education high level of power consumption. Moreover, gender and age had a negative effect on encouragement, whereby men and young people were more willing to pay than women. Therefore, the communication program for SG rooftop PV should focus on men and the younger.

Conclusion

In the research area, the number of households who install SG rooftop PV was very small. However, after the authors conducted surveys and released information about SG rooftop PV, the investigated people understood. Men and young people will have high encouragement for SG rooftop PV investment than women and older people. Education was the factor that affects most on encouragement for the SG rooftop PV investment.

Recommendations

The authors declare that there are no conflict interests and this is the original research that is not published anywhere before

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Author Information

Nguyen Thi Hai Yen

Faculty of Economics, Tay Nguyen University, Vietnam.

567 Le Duan Street, Buon Ma Thuot City, Daklak Province, Vietnam
